

An English translation of the paper of Max Planck (1916)

“Über die absolute Entropie einatomiger Körper”

or: “On the absolute entropy of monatomic bodies”

to provide a readable version of the German content.

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Version-1 / March 31, 2024

References

Planck, M., 1916: Über die absolute Entropie einatomiger Körper [On the absolute entropy of monatomic bodies]. *Sitzb. Kön. Preuss. Akad. Wiss.*, **31**, 653–667, URL <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/93032#page/707/mode/1up>.

Uncertainties/alternatives in the translation are indicated (in blue) with *italic terms*, together with some additional footnotes (indicated with *P. Marquet* or sometimes in *magenta*).

I have written in **bold** those parts of the text that deal in particular with the problem of determining the “**zero-point energy**” (“*Nullpunktenergie*”). It is indeed for this aspect that I felt the need to translate the 2 thesis memoirs (1879 for the Doctor dissertation; 1880 for the Habilitation) and the 5 articles (1887 about the conservation of energy; 1915a,b,c and 1916 about the absolute definition of the entropy; 1943 about the discovery of quanta in physics), all written in German by Max Planck.

I have, of course, kept the original text of Planck (in black) unchanged, while sometimes including additional notes (in blue).

Do not hesitate to contact me in case of mistakes or any trouble in the English translation from the German text.

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On the absolute entropy of monatomic bodies

by Max Planck (8 June 1916)

1 Introduction (p.653-655)

§ 1. The question of the value of the absolute entropy of a body, in the sense of Nernst's heat theorem, is closely related to that of the physical structure of the phase space, which is determined by the size, shape and position of the elementary areas of probability. As soon as this is known, the thermodynamic, integer probability W , and from this the entropy of the body $k \cdot \ln(W)$ can be calculated using a clear combinatorial procedure¹.

If, for example, the phase space contains a triple infinite number of elementary regions, so that a certain elementary region is characterized by 3 independent atomic numbers n, n', n'' , then the thermodynamic characteristic function results in Ψ ², i.e. the negative quotient of the free energy F and the temperature³ T :⁴

$$\Psi = -\frac{F}{T} = k \ln \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n''=0}^{\infty} p_{n n' n''} \cdot \exp \left(-\frac{\bar{U}_{n n' n''}}{k T} \right) \right]. \quad (1)$$

From this the energy:⁵

$$U - U_{ref} = T^2 \cdot \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial T} \quad (2)$$

and the entropy:⁶

$$S - S_{ref} = \Psi + T \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial T} = \Psi + \frac{U - U_{ref}}{T}. \quad (3)$$

Here $\bar{U}_{n n' n''}$ means the average energy in the elementary region $(n n' n'')$, and the integer p means the ratio of the size of this region to that of the elementary region (000).

The following rules apply to the determination of the elementary areas. If ϕ_1, ϕ_2, \dots denotes the position coordinates, ψ_1, ψ_2, \dots the corresponding momentum coordinates⁷ of the phase space, then the boundary surfaces of the elementary regions are determined by the equations

$$g = n h, \quad g' = n' h, \quad g'' = n'' h, \quad (4)$$

¹ Note that in all next relationships, "k" is the Planck-Boltzmann's constant / P. Marquet.

² Note that the notation and the meaning of Ψ correspond to the first of the two "characteristic functions" $\psi = S - U/T$ and $\psi' = S - (U + PV)/T$ introduced first by the French scientist François Massieu in 1869, thus before that the (unnamed) functions $\psi = \epsilon - t\eta$ (for $F = U - TS$) and $\zeta = \epsilon + p\nu - t\eta$ (for $G = U + PV - TS$) will be introduced by Gibbs (1875-78), and also before that the free-energy function $F = U - TS$ will be introduced (and named) by Helmholtz (1882-83). Max Planck has used and studied the Massieu's function $\psi = -F/T$ in all his German papers and book, with the interest that they are modified entropy functions and, as such, are more suitable for direct studies of maximum entropy states, for instance / P. Marquet.

³ Note that from the two relationships $\Psi = -F/T$ and $F = -k T \ln(Z)$, where Z is the partition function defined in statistical physics, the Massieu's characteristic function Ψ defined by (1) simply corresponds to $\Psi = k \ln(Z)$, with therefore the partition function Z made of the triple sum forming the argument of the logarithm in (1) / P. Marquet.

⁴ Max Planck, Verhandl. d. Deutsch. Phys. Ges. 17, S. 444. 1915 (Namely: "Die Quantenhypothese für Molekeln mit mehreren Freiheitsgraden / The quantum hypothesis for molecules with multiple degrees of freedom" (Erste und zweite Mitteilung / First and second communication). Berichte der Deutschen Physikalischen Gesellschaft (Reports of the German Physical Society), Vol.17, N°24, p.407-418 and p.438-451 / P. Marquet).

⁵ In fact, nowadays we know that only the difference in internal energy $U - U_{ref}$ can be computed from (2) and the Massieu's function $\Psi = k \ln(Z)$ depending on the statistical-physics partition function Z . / P. Marquet

⁶ Like in (2) (a priori) only the difference in entropy $S - S_{ref}$ can be computed in (3) from the Massieu's function $\Psi = k \ln(Z)$ depending on the statistical-physics partition function Z . However, the Third-law hypothesis and the Planck's absolute definition of S corresponds to $S_{ref} = 0$ / P. Marquet

⁷ Note that the position coordinates ψ_1, ψ_2, \dots do not correspond to the specific (atomic) characteristic function noted $\psi = \Psi/N$ by Max Planck and introduced in the following / P. Marquet).

where g, g', g'' denote certain functions of the phase coordinates which are characteristic of the structure of the phase space, and n, n', n'' denote mutually independent positive integers, including zero.

The relationship then applies to a differential region of the phase space:

$$dG = \int \int \int \int \int \int_{g, g', g''}^{g+dg, g'+dg', g''+dg''} \dots d\phi_1 d\phi_2 \dots d\psi_1 d\psi_2 \dots = d(g^f) \cdot d(g'^{f'}) \cdot d(g''^{f''}) \cdot \quad (5)$$

Here the integration is to be extended over all phase points which lie within the specified limits, and $f + f' + f''$ is the number of degrees of freedom of the system, of which f, f' and f'' are coherent with each other.

According to these determinations, the elementary region $(n n' n'')$, defined by the boundaries $g_n, g_{n+1}, g'_{n'}, g'_{n'+1}, g''_{n''}, g''_{n''+1}$, has the size:

$$\int_n^{n+1} \int_{n'}^{n'+1} \int_{n''}^{n''+1} dG = (g_{n+1}^f - g_n^f) \cdot (g'_{n'+1}^{f'} - g'_{n'}^{f'}) \cdot (g''_{n''+1}^{f''} - g''_{n''}^{f''}) \cdot \quad (6)$$

Therefore⁸, the size of the elementary area (000) is $h^{f+f'+f''}$, and the values p and \bar{U} are obtained as:

$$p_{n n' n''} = \left[(n+1)^f - n^f \right] \cdot \left[(n'+1)^{f'} - n'^{f'} \right] \cdot \left[(n''+1)^{f''} - n''^{f''} \right], \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{U}_{n n' n''} = \frac{\int_n^{n+1} \int_{n'}^{n'+1} \int_{n''}^{n''+1} U d(g^f) d(g'^{f'}) d(g''^{f''})}{p \cdot h^{f+f'+f''}}, \quad (8)$$

which expressions, inserted in (1), give the value of Ψ and everything else.

This whole calculation is based on the physical hypothesis that within each elementary region the phase points can have arbitrary positions (an assumption which I would like to state explicitly as not yet beyond doubt), especially since the other assumption (that the phase points can only lie at the boundaries of the elementary regions) seems to have certain advantages over it. However, as we will see, this contrast plays only a relatively minor role in the present investigation.

As a preliminary example, the entropy of a single atom should first be determined.

2 First part. (*Entropy for*) A single atom. (p.655-659)

2.1 Atom in a rectangular parallelepiped. (p.655-657)

§ 2. If a point-shaped atom flies around freely in a hollow (*empty*) rectangular parallelepiped of rigid-elastic wall with the edge lengths (a, b, c) , the three components of its velocity remain constant in magnitude, but swap their sign to the opposite at regularly recurring intervals. If m denotes the mass of the atom, (x_0, y_0, z_0) the initial values ($t = 0$) of the coordinates, (ξ_0, η_0, ζ_0) those of the corresponding momentum coordinates, the movement of the atom for all times t is represented by the following 6 equations for the coordinates of the corresponding phase point in the six-dimensional phase space:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x &= \frac{a}{2} - \frac{4a}{\pi^2} \left[\cos(\alpha) + \frac{\cos(3\alpha)}{9} + \frac{\cos(5\alpha)}{25} + \dots \right] \\ y &= \frac{b}{2} - \frac{4b}{\pi^2} \left[\cos(\beta) + \frac{\cos(3\beta)}{9} + \frac{\cos(5\beta)}{25} + \dots \right] \\ z &= \frac{c}{2} - \frac{4c}{\pi^2} \left[\cos(\gamma) + \frac{\cos(3\gamma)}{9} + \frac{\cos(5\gamma)}{25} + \dots \right] \end{aligned} \right\}, \quad (9)$$

⁸ In the next relationships, "h" is the Planck's constant minimal quantum value of action / P. Marquet.

$$\xi = m \frac{dx}{dt} = \pm \xi_0, \quad \eta = m \frac{dy}{dt} = \pm \eta_0, \quad \zeta = m \frac{dz}{dt} = \pm \zeta_0, \quad (10)$$

where are set as abbreviations:

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi}{a} \left(\frac{\xi_0 t}{m} + x_0 \right), \quad \beta = \frac{\pi}{b} \left(\frac{\eta_0 t}{m} + y_0 \right), \quad \gamma = \frac{\pi}{c} \left(\frac{\zeta_0 t}{m} + z_0 \right).$$

For the quantum division of phase space, the theorem that each phase trajectory runs along its entire length within one and the same elementary region is decisive. Since the spatial coordinates (x, y, z) of the atom, as can easily be seen from equations (9), come arbitrarily close to those of any point within the parallelepiped over time (except for certain rational cases which are not relevant to the generality), then each elementary region of the phase space contains all points of the parallelepiped, but only a limited number of points of the region of momentum coordinates (ξ, η, ζ) , and dG decomposes according to (5) into 3 completely independent factors:

$$dG = \iiint \iiint \iiint dx \cdot dy \cdot dz \cdot d\xi \cdot d\eta \cdot d\zeta = dg \cdot dg' \cdot dg''.$$

The 3 degrees of freedom are therefore incoherent, *with accordingly*

$$f = 1, \quad f' = 1, \quad f'' = 1,$$

and

$$dg = \int dx \cdot d\xi, \quad dg' = \int dy \cdot d\eta, \quad dg'' = \int dz \cdot d\zeta.$$

Therefore, by performing the integrations, taking into account that each elementary domain comprises as many positive as negative values of its momentum coordinates:

$$g = a \cdot 2 \xi, \quad g' = b \cdot 2 \eta, \quad g'' = c \cdot 2 \zeta. \quad (11)$$

From these values it follows from (7) $p = 1$, and from (8) with the energy of the atom

$$u = \frac{1}{2m} (\xi^2 + \eta^2 + \zeta^2) = \frac{1}{8m} \left(\frac{g^2}{a^2} + \frac{g'^2}{b^2} + \frac{g''^2}{c^2} \right),$$

$$\bar{u}_{n n' n''} = \frac{1}{h^3} \cdot \int_n^{n+1} \int_{n'}^{n'+1} \int_{n''}^{n''+1} u \cdot dg \cdot dg' \cdot dg'',$$

by integration and taking into account (4):

$$\bar{u}_{n n' n''} = \frac{h^2}{8m} \left(\frac{n^2 + n + 1/3}{a^2} + \frac{n'^2 + n' + 1/3}{b^2} + \frac{n''^2 + n'' + 1/3}{c^2} \right). \quad (12)$$

For the thermodynamic characteristic function of the atom it follows from (1):

$$\psi = k \ln \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n''=0}^{\infty} \exp \left(- \frac{\bar{u}_{n n' n''}}{k T} \right) \right]. \quad (13)$$

The two borderline cases of high and low temperatures are the clearest.

At high temperatures, only the sum terms with large atomic numbers (n, n', n'') make noticeable contributions to the value of the sum. Then the sums can be replaced by integrals and it becomes

$$\psi = k \ln \left[\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \exp\left(-\frac{u}{kT}\right) dn dn' dn'' \right],$$

where the expression (12) has to be inserted for u .

This gives, using the transformation

$$n^2 + n + \frac{1}{3} = \left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{12},$$

and omitting infinitesimally small terms:

$$\psi = k \left\{ \frac{3}{2} \ln \left(\frac{2\pi m k T}{h^2} \right) + \ln(a b c) \right\}. \quad (14)$$

From this and according to (2), the energy $u = T^2 \partial\psi/\partial T$ is

$$\boxed{u = \frac{3}{2} k T},$$

and according to (3), *and thus* $s = \psi + u/T = \psi + (3/2) k = \psi + k (3/2) \ln(e)$ with $e = \exp(1)$, the entropy

$$\boxed{s = k \left\{ \frac{3}{2} \ln \left(\frac{2\pi e m k T}{h^2} \right) + \ln(a b c) \right\}}, \quad (15)$$

only distinguished from the expression ψ *given by (14)* by the term with $e = \exp(1)$.

At low temperatures, however, the sum (13) is limited to the first term, i.e. *from (12) with $n = 0$* :

$$\psi(T \approx 0) = -\frac{1}{T} \cdot \bar{u}_{000} = -\frac{1}{T} \cdot \frac{h^2}{24m} \left(\frac{1}{a^2} + \frac{1}{b^2} + \frac{1}{c^2} \right). \quad (16)$$

From this and from the entropy $s = 0$, either according to (2) or directly from (12), the zero point energy is:⁹

$$\boxed{u(T \approx 0) = \bar{u}_{000} = \frac{h^2}{24m} \left(\frac{1}{a^2} + \frac{1}{b^2} + \frac{1}{c^2} \right)}. \quad (17)$$

2.2 Atom in a hollow (*empty*) sphere (p.657-659)

§ 3. If an atom flies around freely in a hollow (*empty*) sphere of radius R with a rigid-elastic wall, it remains permanently in the plane of a largest circle and describes distances of equal length with a constant velocity q , the directions of which always form the same angle when hitting the wall form α . For $\alpha = 0$ the atom moves directly along the wall, for $\alpha = \pi/2$ it flies back and forth through the center.

⁹ *This hypothesis "s = 0 at T ≈ 0 K" is similar to the third-law of thermodynamics, which is valid for the more stable solid states, but here applied to a gas. If the zero point entropy \bar{s}_{000} does not cancel out at 0 K for a gas, then (16) should be replaced by: $\psi(T \approx 0) = \bar{s}_{000} - \bar{u}_{000}/T$, and (17) by $u(T \approx 0) = \bar{u}_{000} - T \cdot \bar{s}_{000}$, with \bar{s}_{000} to be determined. / P. Marquet.*

Of the 3 degrees of freedom of this system, 2 are coherent with each other, since the position of the orbital plane has no influence at all on the quantum division of the phase space, so

$$f = 1, \quad f' = 2,$$

and from (5):

$$dG = dg \cdot dg'^2,$$

and from (7):

$$p = 2n' + 1,$$

and from (8):

$$\bar{u}_{nn'} = \frac{\int_n^{n+1} \int_{n'}^{n'+1} u \cdot dg \cdot dg'^2}{(2n' + 1) \cdot h^3}, \quad (18)$$

and from (1):

$$\psi = k \ln \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n'=0}^{\infty} (2n' + 1) \cdot \exp \left(-\frac{\bar{u}_{nn'}}{kT} \right) \right]. \quad (19)$$

I have carried out the determination of g and g' in a work about “the physical structure of phase space” that will soon appear in the Annals of Physics¹⁰ and allow me to use the results here, which is all the easier, as the names here are exactly the same as there. Namely it is:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} g &= 2mRq [\sin(\alpha) - \alpha \cos(\alpha)] \\ g' &= 2\pi mRq \cos(\alpha) \end{aligned} \right\}. \quad (20)$$

Since the energy $u = m q^2/2$ cannot be conveniently expressed in terms of g and g' , the calculation of (19) for the general case leads to very complicated expressions, but it becomes easy if one again restricts oneself to the consideration of high or low temperatures.

At high temperatures (large atomic numbers n and n') one can replace $\bar{u}_{nn'}$ by the value of u at any point in the elementary domain (nn'), and (replace) the summation in (19) by an integration. Then, taking into account (5), (6) and (7), we get:

$$\psi = k \ln \left[\int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \exp \left(-\frac{u}{kT} \right) \cdot \frac{dg \cdot dg'^2}{h^3} \right].$$

To carry out this integration, we can use q and α as integration variables instead of g and g'^2 , by means of equations (20) and the following relationship:

$$dg \cdot dg'^2 = 16\pi^2 m^3 R^3 q^2 \sin^2(\alpha) \cos(\alpha) d\alpha dq.$$

Then it results:

$$\psi = k \left\{ \frac{3}{2} \ln \left(\frac{2\pi m k T}{h^2} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{4}{3} R^3 \pi \right) \right\}, \quad (21)$$

¹⁰ Probably in volume 50, 1916 (*Indeed: 1916. Die physikalische Struktur des Phasenraumes [The physical structure of phase space], Annalen der Physik Leipzig, Vol.50, p.385-418 / P. Marquet*).

and from this, according to (2), the energy $u = T^2 \partial\psi/\partial T$ is:

$$u = \frac{3}{2} k T,$$

and furthermore, according to (3), the entropy $s = \psi + u/T = \psi + (3/2) k = \psi + k (3/2) \ln(e)$ with $e = \exp(1)$ is:

$$s = k \left\{ \frac{3}{2} \ln \left(\frac{2 \pi e m k T}{h^2} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{4}{3} R^3 \pi \right) \right\}. \quad (22)$$

A comparison with (15) shows that for high temperatures the entropy of a single atom in a hollow (*empty*) sphere is the same as in a rectangular parallelepiped of the same volume, and it will not be too hazardous to conclude from this that this theorem is generally valid for any shape of the cavity (*or hollow (empty) space*).¹¹

At low temperatures, in the expression (19) of ψ the double sum reduces to its first term, i.e. to:

$$\psi = - \frac{\bar{u}_{00}}{T},$$

where, according to (18), the zero point energy is:

$$\bar{u}_{00} = \frac{1}{h^3} \int_0^h \int_0^{h^2} \frac{m}{2} \cdot q^2 \cdot dg \cdot dg'^2. \quad (23)$$

Carrying out the integration is complicated but shows, by comparison with (17), that the zero point energy is essentially dependent on the shape (*dimensions/volume*) of the cavity.¹²

3 Second part. A large number of atoms with all coherent degrees of freedom. (p.659-665)

§ 4. If we now move on to considering a large number N of point-like atoms, in order to get to know the structure of the phase space, we first have to ask again about the shape of the path that a phase point follows in this $6N$ -dimensional space during the motion of the atoms, and this question cannot be answered until we make a premise about the forces with which the atoms act on one another during a collision.

We shall therefore first introduce the most obvious hypothesis that these forces absolutely obey the laws of classical mechanics, and also the further well-known hypothesis that the phase point comes arbitrarily close to every point on its energy surface $U = const.$ in the course of its movement.

Then the elementary regions of the phase space are bounded by a single type of surfaces g , namely the surfaces of constant energy:

$$U = U_0, U_1, U_2, \dots U_n, \dots$$

¹¹ Note that the only difference between (15) and (22) are the second logarithm terms of pure constants independent of the true variables (i.e. the mass m and the absolute temperature T) / P. Marquet..

¹² Note that, similarly, the second logarithms in (14) or (21) for the characteristic function ψ , and in (15) or (22) for the entropy s , are exactly the volume of the cavity: " abc " and " $(4/3) \pi R^3$ " for a rectangular parallelepiped and a sphere of radius R , respectively / P. Marquet..

There is therefore only a single series of atomic numbers n , and the $3N$ degrees of freedom of the system are all coherent with each other.

In our formulae, $f = 3N$, and according to (5):

$$dG = \iiint_U^{U+dU} \dots d\phi_1 d\phi_2 \dots d\psi_1 d\psi_2 \dots = d(g^{3N}) . \quad (24)$$

According to (6) and (4), the elementary region (n) has the size:

$$G_{n+1} - G_n = g_{n+1}^{3N} - g_n^{3N} = [(n+1)^{3N} - (n)^{3N}] h^{3N} , \quad (25)$$

where

$$G_n = (nh)^{3N} . \quad (26)$$

Now we want to assume that N is so large that in the difference (25) the subtrahend $(n)^{3N}$ against the minuend $(n+1)^{3N}$ disappears, which is always and only true if

$$n \ll N , \quad (27)$$

i.e. if only those members of the sum in (1) whose ordinal number n is of a smaller order of magnitude than N can be considered for the formation of the characteristic function Ψ . The lower the temperature, the easier it is to fulfill this requirement.

Then equation (25) turns into:

$$G_{n+1} - G_n = (n+1)^{3N} h^{3N} . \quad (28)$$

From this it follows from (7):

$$p_n = (n+1)^{3N} \quad (29)$$

and according to (8) with the same degree of approximation:

$$\bar{U}_n = \frac{\int_n^{n+1} U \cdot dG}{G_{n+1} - G_n} = U_{n+1} , \quad (30)$$

i.e. the average energy in the elementary region (n) bounded by the areas $U = U_n$ and $U = U_{n+1}$ is equal to the energy U_{n+1} , up to vanishingly small.

Here U , according to (24) and (26), is determined by the relation:

$$G_n = \iiint_{U=0}^{U=U_n} \dots d\phi_1 d\phi_2 \dots d\psi_1 d\psi_2 \dots = (nh)^{3N} . \quad (31)$$

These values, inserted in (1), result in the characteristic function of the body:

$$\Psi = k \ln \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (n+1)^{3N} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{U_{n+1}}{kT}\right) \right] \approx k \ln \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (n)^{3N} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{U_n}{kT}\right) \right] . \quad (32)$$

As can be seen, the ordinal numbers now no longer refer to the elementary domains, but to the boundary surfaces of the elementary domains, and this justifies the assertion made at the end of § 1 that it makes no essential difference here whether one assumes the phase points to be located inside the elementary domains or accumulated at their boundaries. This will always be the case when there are many coherent degrees of freedom.

§ 5. In the above calculations, we have made use of a prerequisite which has not been explicitly emphasised anywhere so far, but which is nevertheless essential for the validity of the derived formulae: namely that all N atoms of the body under consideration are dissimilar. Indeed, only in this case does a certain point in phase space correspond to each physical state of the body defined in a microscopically precise sense. If, however, the body contains groups of atoms of the same type, this is no longer the case. Instead, a more or less large number of physically completely equivalent points in the phase space are assigned to a certain physical state of the body, since a certain point in the phase space requires certain coordinates and velocities for each individual atom. As many permutations as the atoms of the same type allow, just as many phase points correspond to a certain physical state. For ease of expression, I will therefore distinguish between “phase point” and “state point.”

If N_1, N_2, N_3, \dots of the N atoms are identical, then each state point $N_1! N_2! N_3! \dots = \mathcal{R}$ corresponds to phase points, and the entire phase space (as well as each elementary region of the phase space) decomposes into \mathcal{R} physically completely congruent pieces, of which one can pick out any one and regard it as a representative of the “state space” or a “state region.” The size of a state region is the \mathcal{R} th part of the corresponding phase region.

The question now arises as to whether and which modifications are to be made in this case to the above equations to determine the thermodynamic characteristic function. This question cannot be decided a priori (just as the thermodynamic probability W cannot be derived a priori), but can only be answered by making a determination that is as generally useful and as plausible as possible, trusting in the feasibility of an appropriate theory, which leads to correct results in all controllable cases. The following sentence should be understood in this sense, which, as far as I can see so far, generally solves the problem at hand.

If among the N atoms of the body N_1, N_2, N_3, \dots are similar, then equations (29), (30) and (32) remain completely unchanged. In fact, the quantities p_n and \bar{U}_n retain their meaning whether one refers to the phase space or to the state space, since both quantities represent ratios whose value cannot be influenced by a uniform change in the numerator and denominator. On the other hand, equation (31), which is used to determine the size of U_n , changes in that the relationship (26) on which it is based is not valid for the phase space, but for the state space. If we continue to relate the area size G_n to the phase space, then in the case of similar atoms it can be assumed to be \mathcal{R} times as large as the value given in (26), and equation (31) turns into:

$$G_n = N_1! N_2! N_3! \dots (n h)^{3N} . \quad (33)$$

More specifically, for all similar atoms one obtains:

$$G_n = \iiint \int_{U=0}^{U=U_n} \dots d\phi_1 d\phi_2 \dots d\psi_1 d\psi_2 \dots = N! (n h)^{3N} . \quad (34)$$

§ 6. We restrict the further calculation to the case of a gas consisting of N similar atoms with mass m . Then the energy, with the same designation as in § 2:

$$U = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{k=1}^N (\xi_k^2 + \eta_k^2 + \zeta_k^2) , \quad (35)$$

and the limit values U_n of the energy are determined according to (34) by the relationship:

$$G_n = \iiint \int_{U=0}^{U=U_n} \dots dx_k dy_k dz_k \dots d\xi_k d\eta_k d\zeta_k \dots = N! (n h)^{3N} . \quad (35a)$$

The integration must be extended for the spatial coordinates of each atom over the entire volume V of the gas, and for the momentum coordinates over all combinations that correspond to a total energy of the gas between 0 and U_n . According to (35), this integration domain can be understood as the volume of a sphere in a $3N$ -dimensional space, of radius $\sqrt{2 m U_n}$, which is equal to

$$\frac{2 \pi^{3N/2}}{3 N \cdot \left(\frac{3N}{2} - 1\right)!} \cdot (2 m U_n)^{3N/2} .$$

From this it follows:

$$V^N \cdot \frac{2 \pi^{3N/2}}{3 N \cdot \left(\frac{3N}{2} - 1\right)!} \cdot (2 m U_n)^{3N/2} = N! (n h)^{3N} ,$$

and, using Stirling's theorem $\ln(N!) \approx N \ln(N) - N$, if smaller terms are omitted:

$$U_n = \frac{3 n^2 h^2 N^{5/3}}{4 \pi e^{5/3} m V^{2/3}} . \quad (36)$$

For abbreviation, let us denote with the corresponding small letters v, u, ψ, s the values of the volume V , the energy U , the characteristic function Ψ and the entropy S divided by the atomic number N , and further sets the number:

$$\tau = \frac{h^2}{4 \pi e^{5/3} m v^{2/3} k T} , \quad (37)$$

then from (32) it follows as a characteristic function:

$$\psi = \frac{k}{N} \cdot \ln \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} [n \cdot \exp(-\tau n^2)]^{3N} \right] , \quad (38)$$

further from (2) and from (37) leading to $u = T^2 \partial\psi/\partial T = -(T \tau) \partial\psi/\partial\tau$, as an atomic energy:

$$u = 3 k T \tau \cdot \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^2 \cdot [n \exp(-\tau n^2)]^{3N}}{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} [n \exp(-\tau n^2)]^{3N}} , \quad (39)$$

and from (3) as an atomic entropy:

$$s = \psi + \frac{u}{T} . \quad (40)$$

For high temperatures ($\tau \propto 1/T \ll 1$) one can always consider n to be large and write the sum in (38) as an (Eulerian) integral, and therefore:

$$\psi = \frac{k}{N} \cdot \ln \left[\int_0^{\infty} [n \exp(-\tau n^2)]^{3N} \cdot dn \right] , \quad (41)$$

$$\psi = -\frac{3}{2} k \ln(2 e \tau) = \frac{3}{2} k \ln \left(\frac{2 \pi m k T (e v)^{2/3}}{h^2} \right) . \quad (42)$$

This result can also be obtained in a much simpler way if one considers that, because of the size of N , the largest member of the sum in (38) –namely the member with the ordinal number $n' = 1/\sqrt{2\tau}$ *computed with* $\partial/\partial n' [n' \exp(-\tau n'^2)] = 0$, to be regarded as an integer because of the smallness of τ –

exceeds all other members in size in such a way that the value of the whole infinite sum is reduced to this single member. Therefore, *the characteristic function* ψ given by (42) follows directly from (38)¹³.

Furthermore *the internal energy follows* from (2) and $u = T^2 \partial\psi/\partial T$ applied to (42) with $\tau \propto 1/T$ given by (37), or *directly* from (39), to give:

$$\boxed{u = \frac{3}{2} k T}, \quad (43)$$

and *the entropy follows from* (40) and (37), leading to:

$$s = \psi + \frac{u}{T} = -\frac{3}{2} k \ln(2\tau), \quad \text{or: } \boxed{s = \frac{3}{2} k \ln\left(\frac{2\pi e^{5/3} m v^{2/3} k T}{h^2}\right)}. \quad (44)$$

P. Marquet: Note that the relationship (44) may be put into a formulation similar to (15) or (22), with as expected the second logarithm term only depending on a pure geometric value – made of the product of the pure constant term $e = \exp(1)$ by the volume (v), leading to:

$$s(T, v, m) = k \left\{ \frac{3}{2} \ln\left(\frac{2\pi e m k T}{h^2}\right) + \ln(e v) \right\}. \quad (44\text{bis})$$

Moreover, it is possible to rewrite (44) to arrive at what is nowadays called the “Sackur-Tetrode” formulation for the absolute entropy of a monoatomic gas, namely any of the equivalent formulas:

$$S(T, v, m) = N \cdot s = R \cdot \ln\left[\frac{e^{5/2} v (2\pi m k T)^{3/2}}{h^3}\right], \quad (44\text{ter})$$

$$S(T, V, M) = R \cdot \ln\left\{\frac{5}{2} + \frac{3}{2} \ln(T) + \ln(V) + \frac{3}{2} \ln(M) + \ln\left[\frac{(2\pi k)^{3/2}}{h^3 N^{5/2}}\right]\right\}, \quad (44\text{ter-T-V})$$

$$S(T, P, M) = R \cdot \ln\left\{\frac{5}{2} + \frac{5}{2} \ln(T) - \ln(P) + \frac{3}{2} \ln(M) + \ln\left[\frac{(2\pi)^{3/2} k^{5/2}}{h^3 N^{3/2}}\right]\right\}, \quad (44\text{ter-T-P})$$

where N is the (atomic) Avogadro’s number, $R = N k \approx 8.314$ the gas constant, $M = N m$ the molar mass, $V = N v$ the molar volume and $P V = R T$ the molar gas equation. the last logarithm term in (44ter-T-P) has the value of about 18.222 85 SI-unit.

This expression for the entropy of an ideal monatomic gas *given by (44) or (44bis)*, which differs from the value derived above in (22) for the entropy of a single atom only by **an additive member**, is completely identical with the expression determined by Stern¹⁴ and von Tetrode¹⁵ in quite different ways and well confirmed by experience. Differently, Sackur¹⁶, who was the first to calculate the absolute entropy of a gas from the assumption of finite elementary regions of probability, obtained the value (22),

¹³ Indeed, with the sole term $n = n' = 1/\sqrt{2}\tau$ in the sum (38), we get $\psi = (k/N) \cdot \ln[n' \exp(-\tau n'^2)]^{3N} = (k/N) \cdot (3N) [\ln(n') - \tau n'^2]$, which leads to (42) with $\ln(n') = (-1/2) \ln(2\tau)$ and $-\tau n'^2 = -(1/2) \ln(e) / P$. Marquet.

¹⁴ O. Stern, Phys. Zeitschr. 14, S. 629, 1913.

¹⁵ H. Tetrode, Ann. d. Phys. 38, S. 434, 1912. Ber. d. Akad. d. Wiss. v. Amsterdam, 27. Februar und 27. März, 1915, Gleichung (equation) (16).

¹⁶ O. Sackur, Ann. d. Phys. 36, S. 958, 1911 ; 40, S. 67, 1913.

while the entropy constant in the expressions of Sommerfeld¹⁷ and Keesom¹⁸ show even greater deviations.

In contrast, Nernst's¹⁹ hypothesis of zero-point radiation has recently led to a value of the entropy constant that differs only slightly from Tetrode's value, and Nernst's calculation, in contrast to those of Stern and Tetrode, is valid not only for the ideal gas state, but also for arbitrarily low values of temperature. According to this Nernst's hypothesis, the total energy of the gas, including the zero-point energy, is represented by the expression:

$$(Nernst's\ value:) \quad \frac{U}{N} = u = \frac{3}{2} \frac{h\nu}{\exp\left(\frac{h\nu}{kT}\right) - 1} + \frac{3}{2} h\nu, \quad (45)$$

whereby the abbreviation (*for the frequency ν*) is:

$$(Nernst's\ value:) \quad \nu = \frac{h}{4\pi m v^{2/3}}. \quad (46)$$

The comparison *of (45)* with the expression (39) shows the following:

- for high temperatures, the values agree, as is natural; and
- for lower temperatures, according to (39), the zero-point energy is:²⁰

$$\boxed{u_0 = 3kT\tau = \frac{3h^2}{4\pi e^{5/3} m v^{2/3}}}, \quad (47)$$

whereas, according to *the Nernst's hypothesis leading to (45) and for $T \approx 0$, the first term vanishes and thus $u_0 \approx (3/2) h\nu$, with ν given by (46) leading to:*

$$(Nernst's\ value:) \quad u_0 = \frac{3h^2}{8\pi m v^{2/3}} = \frac{3h^2}{4\pi e^{5/3} m v^{2/3}} \times \frac{e^{5/3}}{2}, \quad (48)$$

which is larger *than (47)* in the ratio $e^{5/3}/2 \approx 2.65$.

P. Marquet: the proof of (47) is obtained by computing the sums over $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, n, \dots$ (up to $+\infty$) both at the numerator and the denominator of (39), to give:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u &= (3kT\tau) \cdot \frac{0 + (e^{-\tau})^{3N} + 4(2e^{-4\tau})^{3N} + \dots + n^2 (ne^{-(n^2)\tau})^{3N} + \dots}{0 + (e^{-\tau})^{3N} + (2e^{-4\tau})^{3N} + \dots + (ne^{-(n^2)\tau})^{3N} + \dots} \\ u &= (3kT\tau) \cdot \frac{1 + 4(2e^{-3\tau})^{3N} + \dots + n^2 (ne^{-(n^2-1)\tau})^{3N} + \dots}{1 + (2e^{-3\tau})^{3N} + \dots + (ne^{-(n^2-1)\tau})^{3N} + \dots} \\ u_0 &\approx (3kT\tau) \cdot \frac{1}{1} = 3kT\tau = \frac{3h^2}{4\pi e^{5/3} m v^{2/3}} \quad \dots \quad i.e. \quad (47). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (39bis)$$

The third line is obtained from the second with the approximation $T \ll 1$ and thus $\tau \propto 1/T \gg 1$, with moreover $N \gg 1$ leading to $(e^{-(n^2-1)\tau})^{3N} \ll e^{-\tau} \ll 1$ by very far. Therefore only the first two unity terms can be retained at the numerator and the denominator, leading to $u_0 \approx 3kT\tau \dots$ QED.

¹⁷ A. Sommerfeld, Göttinger Vorträge über die kinetische Theorie der Materie und der Elektrizität (*Göttingen lectures on the kinetic theory of matter and electricity*) 1914, S. 125 (B. G. Teubner).

¹⁸ H. Keesom, Phys. Zeitschr. 14, S. 665, 1913; 15, S. 695, 1914.

¹⁹ W. Nernst, Verhandl. d. Deutschen Phys. Ges. 18, S. 83. 1916.

²⁰ Note that Max Planck made a typo in the numerator of (47), with "h" instead of "h²" / P. Marquet.

If expression (39) for the energy of a monatomic gas appears at least debatable compared to Nernst's expression (45), on closer inspection it turns out to be completely useless. Because its size is discontinuous with respect to τ and T , so that a specific heat cannot be defined at all.

This can be recognized either by a direct examination of the sums in (39), or more conveniently by considering that the energy of the gas changes in steps with the temperature not only in a microscopic but also in a macroscopic sense, since according to (36) the jumps increase in size with increasing atomic number n (i.e. with increasing temperature).

The hypothesis introduced at the beginning of § 4 (that the collisions of atoms take place according to the laws of classical mechanics), must therefore be viewed as unfeasible. This insight seems to me to be worth investigating.

4 Third part. A large number of atoms with mutually incoherent degrees of freedom. (p.665-667)

§ 7. After the second part of this work demonstrated the untenability of the assumption of purely coherent degrees of freedom, there now appears to be no other way out than to assume that the atomic movements are incoherent.

Therefore, only the three degrees of freedom of each individual atom are coherent, i.e.

$$f = 3, \quad f' = 3, \quad f'' = 3, \quad \dots$$

and equation (35a) is replaced by the following:

$$\iiint \int_{0,0,0}^{n,n',n''} \dots dx dy dz \dots d\xi d\eta d\zeta \dots = N! (nh)^3 (n'h)^3 \dots = \left(\frac{N}{e}\right)^N (nh)^3 (n'h)^3 \dots, \quad (49)$$

which gives by decomposition for a single atom:

$$\iiint \int_{g=0}^{g=g_n} dx dy dz d\xi d\eta d\zeta = \frac{N}{e} g_n^3 = \frac{N}{e} (nh)^3, \quad (50)$$

and for a differential field:

$$\iiint \int_g^{g+dg} dx dy dz d\xi d\eta d\zeta = \frac{N}{e} d(g^3), \quad (51)$$

If one integrates over the space and momentum coordinates by denoting the size of the velocity with q , the result is:

$$V \cdot m^3 \cdot d\left(\frac{4}{3} \pi q^3\right) = \frac{N}{e} d(g^3)$$

or (*by integration*):

$$q = \frac{g}{m} \left(\frac{3}{4 \pi e v}\right)^{1/3}, \quad (\text{thus with the constant of integration} = 0?) \quad (52)$$

and likewise:

$$q' = \frac{g'}{m} \left(\frac{3}{4 \pi e v}\right)^{1/3}, \quad \text{etc.}$$

The further calculation can be carried out in the same way as before. First, according to (8) the average energy in the elementary domain ($n n' n'' \dots$) is:

$$\bar{U}_{n n' n'' \dots} = \frac{\int_n^{n+1} \int_{n'}^{n'+1} \int_{n''}^{n''+1} \dots U d(g^3) d(g'^3) d(g''^3) \dots}{p \cdot h^{3N}}, \quad (53)$$

where according to (7) with $f = f' = f'' = \dots = 3$:

$$p = [(n+1)^3 - (n)^3] \cdot [(n'+1)^3 - (n')^3] \cdot [(n''+1)^3 - (n'')^3] \dots \quad (54)$$

and according to (35) and (52):

$$U = \frac{1}{2m} \cdot \left(\frac{3}{4\pi e v} \right)^{2/3} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^N (g^2 + g'^2 + g''^2 + \dots); \quad (55)$$

i.e. by carrying out the integration, taking into account the limits (4) with $g = nh, g' = n'h, \dots$:

$$\bar{U}_{n n' n'' \dots} = \frac{3 h^2}{10 m} \cdot \left(\frac{3}{4\pi e v} \right)^{2/3} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^N \left(\frac{(n+1)^5 - (n)^5}{(n+1)^3 - (n)^3} + \frac{(n'+1)^5 - (n')^5}{(n'+1)^3 - (n')^3} + \dots \right). \quad (56)$$

This relationship (56) is indeed a consequence of the multiple integrations in (53), like in the following one with $g = nh$, with U given by the sum in (55), with p given by (54) and h^3 (for one of the N atoms) at the denominator:

$$\frac{1}{2m} \int_n^{n+1} \frac{g^2 d(g^3) / h^3}{(n+1)^3 - (n)^3} = \frac{1}{2m} \int_n^{n+1} \frac{3 h^5 n^4 dn / h^3}{(n+1)^3 - (n)^3} = \left(\frac{3 h^2}{10 m} \right) \cdot \left[\frac{(n+1)^5 - (n)^5}{(n+1)^3 - (n)^3} \right].$$

Inserting this relationship (56) into (1), and after due reduction, gives the expression of the thermodynamic characteristic function related to an atom:

$$\psi = \frac{\Psi}{N} = k \ln \left\{ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} [(n+1)^3 - (n)^3] \cdot \exp \left[- \frac{(n+1)^5 - (n)^5}{(n+1)^3 - (n)^3} \cdot \sigma \right] \right\}, \quad (57)$$

where

$$\sigma = \frac{3 h^2}{10 m k T} \cdot \left(\frac{3}{4\pi e v} \right)^{2/3} \quad (58)$$

is set as an abbreviation.

For high temperatures ($\sigma \ll 1$) you can write the sum in (57) as an integral, namely:

$$\psi = k \cdot \ln \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left[3 n^2 \exp \left(- \frac{5}{3} n^2 \sigma \right) \right] \cdot dn \right],$$

and taking into account (58):

$$\psi = \frac{3}{2} k \ln \left(\frac{2 \pi m k T (e v)^{2/3}}{h^2} \right), \quad (59)$$

which agrees exactly with (42) and Tetrode's value, *and thus with the same absolute entropy (44)*:

$$s = \frac{3}{2} k \ln \left(\frac{2 \pi e^{5/3} m v^{2/3} k T}{h^2} \right). \quad (44)$$

For low temperatures ($\sigma \gg 1$), on the other hand, (57) with only the first-order term $n = 0$ yields:

$$\psi \approx k \ln \{ \exp[-\sigma] \} = -k \sigma = -\frac{3 h^2}{10 m} \cdot \frac{1}{T} \cdot \left(\frac{3}{4 \pi e v} \right)^{2/3},$$

i.e., according to (2), **the zero point energy**:

$$u_0 = T^2 \cdot \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial T} = \frac{3 h^2}{10 m} \cdot \left(\frac{3}{4 \pi e v} \right)^{2/3} = \overbrace{\left(\frac{3 h^2}{4 \pi e^{5/3} m v^{2/3}} \right)}^{\text{Eq. (47)}} \cdot \overbrace{\left[\frac{2 \pi e}{5} \left(\frac{3}{4 \pi} \right)^{2/3} \right]}^{\approx 1.315} \quad (60)$$

against which the Nernst value (48) is greater in the ratio

$$\frac{5}{4 \pi} \cdot \left(\frac{4 \pi e}{3} \right)^{2/3} \approx 2.014.$$

Notes of P. Marquet: an additional comparison with (47) shows that (60) is greater in the ratio 1.315. Moreover, it is possible to write (60) in terms of either the 2 (molar-)variables $M = N m$ and $V = N v$:

$$U_0 = N u_0 = \left[\frac{3 h^2}{10} \cdot N^{8/3} \cdot \left(\frac{3}{4 \pi e} \right)^{2/3} \right] \cdot \frac{1}{M V^{2/3}} \approx \frac{[6.73 \cdot 10^{-5}]}{M V^{2/3}} \text{ J kg}^{-1}, \quad (60\text{-bis})$$

or equivalently in terms of the 3 variables T , $M = N m$ and $P = R T/V = N k T/V$:

$$U_0 = N u_0 = \left[\frac{3 h^2}{10} \cdot \frac{N^2}{k^{2/3}} \cdot \left(\frac{3}{4 \pi e} \right)^{2/3} \right] \cdot \frac{P^{2/3}}{M T^{2/3}} \approx \frac{[1.64 \cdot 10^{-5}]}{M T^{2/3}} P^{2/3} \text{ J kg}^{-1}. \quad (60\text{-ter})$$

The two numerical values $6.730494791 \cdot 10^{-5} \approx 6.73 \cdot 10^{-5}$ in (60-bis) and $1.639926 \cdot 10^{-5} \approx 1.64 \cdot 10^{-5}$ in (60-ter) are computed from the exact values for h , k and N set in May 2019 for five of the seven SI base units specified in the International System of Quantities²¹ (along with c , already defined as an exact value):

- the Planck constant ($h = 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J s}$);
- the Planck (-Boltzmann) constant ($k = 1.380649 \times 10^{-23} \text{ J K}^{-1}$);
- the Avogadro constant ($N = 6.02214076 \times 10^{23} \text{ mol}^{-1}$);
- the elementary electric charge ($e = 1.602176634 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$); and
- the (previously exact) velocity of light in vacuum ($c = 2.99792458 \times 10^8 \text{ m s}^{-1}$).

The accuracy is of 9 digits for h and N –and thus for the constant in (60-bis). The accuracy is of 7 digits only for k –and thus for the constant in (60-ter).

Note that the energies at 0 K in units of J mol^{-1} can be computed from (60-bis) or (60-ter) via the relationship “ $M U_0$ ” equal to $[6.73 \cdot 10^{-5}] / V^{2/3}$ and $[1.64 \cdot 10^{-5}] \cdot (P/T)^{2/3}$, respectively.

²¹ See: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2019_redefinition_of_the_SI_base_units] and [<https://www.bipm.org/en/publications/si-brochure/>].

(Conclusion of Max Planck:)

For arbitrary temperatures, the execution of the summation in (57) causes at first a certain difficulty, but this can soon be overcome, and I hope to soon be able to communicate a series expansion convenient for the calculation of both the specific heat and the pressure²².

As far as I can see, the resulting formulas form the only possible result of applying the quantum hypothesis to the thermodynamic behavior of a monatomic gas, the density of which is so low that no other form of energy can be considered apart from the kinetic energy of the atoms.

²² *I have not found the paper where these computations of Max Planck may have been published after 1916 / P. Marquet*